

ENHANCING TEACHER COMPETENCE FOR INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

Nutfiyeva Dildora

Tashkent State University of Economics, Uzbekistan

ORCID ID: 0009-0003-8666-5475

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14272113>

Abstract. *Inclusive education in higher education emphasizes the creation of equitable learning environments that promote participation and equal educational opportunities for students with different abilities, regardless of socioeconomic status or cultural background. Teachers are at the center of this process, playing a critical role in designing, teaching, and adapting lessons to meet the needs of diverse learners. Their competence directly determines the success of inclusive education initiatives, especially in ensuring equal opportunities, participation, and outcomes. Recent educational reforms in Uzbekistan, in particular the Presidential Decree PF-5712 adopted on April 29, 2019, emphasize the need to prepare teachers to effectively and sustainably support inclusive education.*

Increasing Teacher Skills for Inclusive Higher Education, which supports the new emphasis on equitable learning environments encompassing diversity and expectation of participation from all students — regardless of ability, socio-economic status or cultural background. At the center of this transformation is the teacher who will design, deliver and adapt learning experiences based on many different student needs. Their competence has direct bearing on the success of inclusive education -the accomplishment of equitable access, participation and outcome for all learners. The recent educational reforms in Uzbekistan and the 29th April 2019 Presidential Decree PF-5712, which aims at improving teacher competence to aid inclusive education, are highlighting the need for inclusivity in education. This decree formulated an overall strategy for inclusive education which will serve as a building block for further development from 2020 - 2025. The plan outlined measurable objectives to guarantee the provision of educational services that meet the needs of the students with disabilities, enhancing focus on the infrastructure, legal system, and educators' qualification upgrading.

The main activities during the initial period, 2020-2022, included strengthening the legal and normative foundations of inclusive education, training qualified personnel to teach, and enhancing the technical and material potential of educational institutions. Pilot projects should be carried out to test and refine the inclusive approach in selected institutions. Later on, between 2023 and 2025, the focus will be on scaling up Inclusive Education to more schools and universities by incorporating aspects of individual approaches, moral spiritual development, and new pedagogical tendencies. Such school reforms thus initiate changes toward an inclusive system and would be directed toward making such an environment where all students feel academically and socially successful.

However, these reforms are extremely dependent on the preparedness and capacity of teachers to implement such changes. In as much as these policy frameworks provide a strong basis, their operationalization presents very significant challenges. One of the greatest barriers is the scarcity of formal training for teachers in inclusive pedagogies, such as Universal Design for Learning (UDL), differentiated instruction, and adaptive teaching strategies. Yet, these methodologies are only imperative in meeting the diverse needs of learners, but also significantly

are underrepresented in traditional teacher education programs. Additionally, higher education institutions, as well, have infrastructural and resource constraints that limit access to adaptive technologies, accessible learning materials, and supportive services. For instance, too many institutions lack facilities that allow students with physical disabilities or sensory impairments to fully engage in campus resources, an added layer to barriers toward inclusion.

As Zulfiya Narbayevna points out we need to connect these reforms with practical actions - allocate resources and enhance teacher skills to make them work. Besides **technical** and **infrastructural** challenges teachers face attitudinal challenges - biases and misconceptions about students with special needs. These biases lead to low expectations or exclusionary practices which hinder inclusive environment. We need not only structural changes but **cultural transformation** within educational institutions focusing on empathy, equity and cultural awareness. The Presidential Decree also requires creation of monitoring systems to track the implementation of the roadmap. These systems will do annual reviews to measure progress, identify gaps and make adjustments to ensure outcomes match the goals.

Public awareness campaigns also play a supporting role to create a positive environment for students with special needs, reduce stigma and promote inclusion. For example, annual reviews of the roadmap have already identified areas that need more support such as expanding teacher training programs, strengthening institutional capacity and ensuring resources are available consistently. This not only holds people accountable but also provides actionable feedback for improvement. Addressing these challenges requires a multi-faceted approach to professional development. Teacher training programs must focus on equipping educators with inclusive pedagogy, cultural responsiveness and the ability to use assistive technology effectively. Training modules should be evidence based and include real life scenarios so teachers can feel confident in inclusive classrooms. Collaborative practices such as peer mentoring, interdisciplinary teaching and professional learning communities can also support teachers to meet the needs of diverse learners. Leveraging insights from international collaborations as mentioned by Makhtuma Qurbonova is also important.

International best practices are useful for designing training programs where local expertise is still developing. Expanding the number of institutions for students with special needs is another key part of these reforms. This means equipping schools and universities with accessible buildings, adaptive technology and tailored learning materials to create a learning environment for all. Recognizing the role of volunteers, student assistants and support staff in inclusive education the roadmap encourages their involvement and a whole community commitment to inclusion. By linking these to teacher training institutions can have a holistic approach to inclusion. It is through the integration of these enhancements with the training of teachers that educational institutions will be able to put in place a holistic approach to inclusiveness. These initiatives epitomize a wider tendency to integrate inclusivity into the higher education system in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Nonetheless, the reforms as noted by Bahodirjon Abdullaev, cannot only be dependent on the existences of policy design but also on appreciation of the implementation processes, availability of capabilities and long term organizational support. In the absence of adequate backing, even the best of intentions of policy formulation will not achieve its objectives. This then highlights how it is critical for institutions to employ strategies that are in tandem with the policies that were defined in the 2019 degree. With the rapid advancement of digital technologies, another opportunity to promote inclusion in education has materialized. As indicated by the research of Olga Kiseleva and Victor Zaitsev, technology can actually transform the learning experience of different students.

For example, the use of assistive technologies with **screen readers, speech to text systems and digital learning** would make it easier for disabled students to join academia. Such instruments in the hands of qualified personnel will not only enhance the learning experience and outcomes but also help in achieving greater inclusion in education. By solving the structural, pedagogical and attitudinal barriers of settlement facing these educators, the inclusive education reforms in Uzbekistan seeks to ensure there is a competent, caring and dynamic cadre of teachers. This entails long term expenditure on improving professional skills, provision of modern technologies and backing of institutions.

Inclusion in higher education however, is equally important in ensuring that the institutional climate allows the success of all students. Building this culture entails not only teacher training but also students, staff and community members in the active process of removing barriers and achieving equity. This guarantees that inclusive education is a concern of everyone with teachers as the change agent. Fostering a culture of inclusion also demands a rethinking of **curricula** and assessment methods in higher education. Curricula should be designed to reflect the diversity of student experiences and provide opportunities for all learners to engage meaningfully with the content. This includes integrating culturally relevant examples, emphasizing collaborative learning, and adopting flexible teaching approaches that accommodate various learning styles and needs. Assessment methods must also evolve to become more inclusive, moving beyond standardized tests to include alternative assessments such as portfolios, presentations, and group projects that allow students to demonstrate their knowledge and skills in diverse ways. Another critical aspect of enhancing teacher competence for inclusive education is addressing the mental health and well-being of both students and educators. Teachers need to be equipped with strategies to identify and support students who may face emotional or psychological challenges. Providing access to counseling services, mental health resources, and peer support programs can create a more supportive environment for all members of the academic community. For educators, addressing their own well-being is equally important, as burnout and stress can undermine their ability to deliver high-quality inclusive education.

Professional development programs should therefore include components that focus on stress management, self-care, and building resilience. In addition to professional development, fostering partnerships between higher education institutions, local communities, and international organizations can play a vital role in advancing inclusive education. Collaborative initiatives can facilitate the exchange of best practices, provide access to resources and expertise, and create opportunities for joint research and innovation. For instance, partnerships with technology companies can help institutions integrate cutting-edge assistive technologies into their learning environments, while collaborations with non-governmental organizations can support awareness campaigns and capacity-building efforts. These partnerships can also serve as platforms for advocacy, driving policy changes that further support inclusive education. Building on the reforms introduced by the Presidential Decree PF-5712, Uzbekistan has the opportunity to position itself as a leader in inclusive education within the region. By prioritizing investment in teacher training, infrastructure, and resource development, the country can create a model for other nations seeking to implement inclusive practices in higher education. Furthermore, Uzbekistan's rich cultural heritage and history of community engagement provide a strong foundation for fostering an inclusive academic culture that values diversity and promotes equity. To ensure the sustainability of these efforts, continuous evaluation and adaptation are essential. Monitoring systems should not only assess the progress of inclusive education initiatives but also identify areas for improvement

and innovation. Feedback from students, educators, and other stakeholders should be actively sought and incorporated into decision-making processes. This participatory approach ensures that reforms remain responsive to the needs of the academic community and aligned with global best practices.

Finally, inclusive education in higher education is not just about meeting the needs of students with disabilities or special needs. It is about creating a learning environment that values and respects the contributions of all students, regardless of their background. This broader perspective emphasizes the role of inclusive education in promoting social cohesion, reducing inequality, and preparing students to succeed in an increasingly diverse and interconnected world. Teachers, as the primary facilitators of this vision, must be equipped with the knowledge, skills, and mindset to lead the way. The journey toward inclusive education is ongoing and requires the collective efforts of educators, policymakers, institutions, and communities. By addressing the challenges and leveraging the opportunities outlined in this article, higher education systems can create environments where all students have the opportunity to reach their full potential. Uzbekistan's recent reforms and commitment to inclusion provide a promising foundation for achieving this vision, with teachers at the forefront of this transformative process.

REFERENCES

1. Abdullaev, B. (2021). *Legal Bases of Formation of Inclusive Education System in Uzbekistan and Achievements*.
2. Ainscow, M. (2020). *Promoting equity in schools: Collaboration and inclusion*. Routledge.
3. Baybayeva, M. X. (2020). *Ta'lim muassasasi rahbarining boshqaruv faoliyatida sog'lom va ijodiy muhitni yaratish mexanizmlarini takomillashtirish* [PhD dissertation].
4. Cameron, C. (2015). *Social pedagogy and working with children and young people: Where care and education meet*. Jessica Kingsley Publishers.
5. Florian, L., & Spratt, J. (2013). Enabling teachers as inclusive practitioners. *Cambridge Journal of Education*, 43(4), 467–484.
6. Freire, P. (1970). *Pedagogy of the oppressed*. Herder and Herder.
7. Kiseleva, O. (2020). *Pedagogical Support for Disabled Students in Higher Education Institutions of Russia*.
8. Madrahimov, A. (2020). *Holistic approaches in inclusive education: A social pedagogical perspective*. Tashkent: Uzbek Academy of Sciences.
9. Mamarajabova, Z. N. (2022). *Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida inklyuziv ta'limdagi islohotlar: muammo va yechim*.
10. Nurgaliyeva, G. (2020). *Inclusive Education in Kazakhstan's Higher Education: Problems and Solutions*.
11. Omonov, G. (2019). *Theoretical foundations of inclusive education in Uzbekistan*. Tashkent: TSUE Press.
12. Qurbonova, M. F. (2023). *Inclusive Education and New Pedagogical Approaches Used in Higher Education System in Uzbekistan*. *International Journal of Scientific Trends*, 6.
13. Shodiyev, I. N. (2020). *Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarda konfliktologik kompetentlikni rivojlantirish* [PhD dissertation].
14. Shomakhmudova, R. (2007). *Theoretical and Practical Foundations of Inclusive Education*. Tashkent: "Razzakov O.J." Printing House.
15. Tazhibayev, R. (2019). *Innovations in Inclusive Education in Kazakhstan*.